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**KAZAKH NEWSPAPERS PUBLISHED IN TASHKENT THE HEROIC
ACTIVITY OF S. KOZHANOV**

The history of Kazakh national press formation at the beginning of the twentieth century in Tashkent city and about the fateful path and activities of the state and public figure - S. Kozhanov will reveal in this article. During the investigation the brief overview of the history was done about the first newspapers published there. The assessment of S. Kozhanov's public activity, his revealed unidentified work on the nation spirituality is given. The scientific idea of the development period of Kazakh culture and the press is discussed.

Keywords: Tashkent, Kazakhstan, Sultanbek, Press, Newspaper.

В статье освещены история становления казахской национальной прессы и судьбоносный путь государственного и общественного деятеля С. Кожановича в начале XX века в Ташкенте. В ходе исследования дается краткий обзор истории первых изданных там газет. Дана оценка неизмеримого труда и общественной деятельности С. Кожанова по вопросам сохранения духовных ценностей нации. Обсуждается научная идея об отдельном периоде развития казахской культуры и прессы.

Ключевые слова: Ташкент, Казах, Султанбек, Пресса, Газета.

Introduction. Wherever there is a nation, spiritual culture continues to develop and flourish. The untainted spirit of the Turkic people, living under the rule of the Russian colonial government, began to awaken over time. At the end of the nineteenth century and the beginning of the twentieth century, the Alash nation entered the historical stage with a new progress. During this difficult period, the first Kazakh books, national newspapers, and modern schools emerged one after another. Kazakh society could not remain uninvolved in the socio-political and enlightenment movements of the time. Among the Kazakhs, the Jadid enlightenment movement spread, and Alash ideology became widely disseminated. Tashkent became one of the spiritual centers with a noble mission on the path of destiny for the Kazakh and Turkic people during this period. The awakening of national consciousness, the enhancement of national qualities, and the vigorous development of national and state education

were brought to the forefront. In response to the demands of the era, the first Kazakh newspapers emerged.

Results and discussions. In the latter half of the 19th century, the first Kazakh newspaper, "Turkistan Ualayty," was published in Tashkent, marking the historical inception of Kazakh journalism. The publication spanned from 1870 to 1882. Although it initially started as a translation publication, it gradually developed into an independent newspaper and was hailed as a pioneer of Kazakh periodicals. "Turkistan Ualayty" began as a supplement to the "Turkestanskije Vedomosti" newspaper, published four times a month, with two issues in Kazakh and the other in Uzbek. The editor of this newspaper was Shakhmardan Ibragimov, a renowned orientalist and a friend of Shokan Ualikhanov. Additionally, "Turkistan Vilaytinin Gazeti" was also well-known as an informational newspaper. Although these publications were initially aimed at tearing off the hypocritical veil of colonial rule, they were not limited to this purpose. They made significant contributions to assessing the current state of our nation. Newspapers served as crucial tools for awakening social thought among the people and influencing the formation and expansion of cultural and literary perspectives. It is worth noting that "Turkistan Ualayty" was not only the first Kazakh periodical but also the first newspaper for all the peoples of Central Asia.

Activists and writers from neighboring ethnic groups such as Kyrgyz, Uzbek, Azerbaijani, and other nationalities also conveyed their nations' noble ideals and voices to the younger generation through newspapers. In the first quarter of the last century, specifically from 1924 to 1927, a Kyrgyz-language newspaper, "Erkin Too" («Erkin tau»), was published in Bishkek.

The first national newspaper of Azerbaijan was published under the name "Ekinchi" (Baku) from 1875 to 1877.

The primary channels for public opinion and literary criticism are newspapers and magazines. "The level of progress of a nation can be seen through the newspapers, magazines, and books circulated among its people," wrote Muhammetzhan Seralin, the publisher of the magazine "Aikap" (1911-1915), in its first issue [1, 1995, p. 58]. Regarding the importance of the press to society, Akhmet Baitursynuly wrote in the first issue of the newspaper "Kazakh" (1913-1918): "First and foremost, a newspaper is the eyes, ears, and mouth of the people. Just as eyes, ears, and mouth are vital to a person, so is a newspaper to the people!" [2, 1989]. These figures, without exception, faithfully fulfilled the historical mission of enlightening the people and uniting the nation.

The newspaper "Birlik Tui" (1917-1918) was published in Tashkent. The initial issues were published by Mustafa Shokay, followed by Khayredin Bolganbayev (issues 6-16) and Sultanbek Kozhanov (issues 17-29). So far, only 29 issues have been discovered. In addition to the aforementioned Kazakh publications, it is also worth mentioning the left-leaning newspaper "Alash" (1916-1917, Tashkent) [3, 2012, pp. 16-37].

In Tashkent, historians and literary scholars have written extensively about the life and work of Sultanbek Kozhanov, a writer and social activist who made

immeasurable contributions to the national spiritual culture. Nonetheless, it is necessary to briefly mention Sultanbek Kozhanov's outstanding contributions and achievements in the field of journalism.

At the end of the 19th century, Sultanbek was born in the remote village of Aksumbe at the northern foot of the Karatau Mountains, and his life unfolded amidst the turbulent events of early 20th-century Turkistan. Sultanbek devoted his short life to serving his people with unwavering loyalty, his fate closely intertwined with that of his nation. He fought alongside his people for a brighter future for the nation. On this path, he experienced happiness, and when his people faced calamities, he sacrificed his life for them. Consequently, during the historical upheavals of national development, S. Kozhanov was accused of being a "nationalist" and labeled as an "enemy of the people." His name remained shrouded in obscurity for a long time. Although Sultanbek's name was rehabilitated during the Soviet era, his true reunion with the people occurred during our nation's independence. Today, in the spiritual firmament of independent Kazakhstan, the star of Sultanbek Kozhanov shines ever brighter.

Research works that showcase the civic, activist, and creative images of S. Kozhanov include those by R. Berdibay, T. Kozhakeev, A. Takenov, T. Kolbayev, M. Koigeldiev, B. Koishybayev, K. Ergobek, Zh. Almashuly, A. Sharip, H. Tursyn, A. Tasybekov, D. Salkynbek, Zh. Simtikov, Zh. Ualkhanova, and A. Abikey. Among the specialized research books on Sultanbek, the works of Zholtai [4, 1994, p. 128], Amantai [5, 1994, 98 p.], and Beibyt [6, 2007, p. 320] are particularly noteworthy.

In recent years, Dr. Haziretali Tursun, a professor with a doctorate in history, has made significant contributions to the study of Sultanbek's role as an activist. Together with his disciple A. Abikey, he unearthed numerous materials from the Tashkent archives, where Sultanbek had lived and worked, thereby enriching the historical foundation of Sultanbek studies. The first volume of the multi-volume work on S. Kozhanov, compiled under H. Tursyn's guidance, is composed entirely of previously unknown archival documents and materials.

Nevertheless, as our nation continues to progress on the path of independent development, the legacy of S. Kozhanov shines ever brighter at the national level, and Sultanbek studies will not stop here. As time passes and eras change, new tasks continually emerge. One of our current critical tasks is to examine the achievements and heritage of those who made historical contributions to the formation of our nation from today's ever-changing perspective. We must uncover and reveal the new, radiant aspects of their legacies from the settled dust of turbulent times. Ultimately, we aim to disseminate the spiritual heritage and invaluable teachings of our great predecessors to benefit the present young generation.

S. Kozhanov spent most of his career in Tashkent and worked in a leadership position in Kazakhstan for only about a year. Nevertheless, he demonstrated remarkable civic spirit and set an example of service to the people, participating in numerous historical tasks that the nation still remembers. His contributions included defining the newly established state borders, promoting economic development, preserving Kazakh national values, and fostering national traditions, literature, and culture. It is well known that the proletarian cultural policies of that era caused

significant harm to national culture. Amidst this threat, Sultanbek endeavored to protect the celebration of Nauryz.

S. Kozhanov frequently advocated for the unity of Turkic peoples in the press. His opinions on "Public Education Work Among the Kyrgyz-Kazakhs" published in the "Sholpan" magazine (Issues 4-5, 1923) placed him alongside great national mentors such as Akhmet Baitursynuly. He stated, "If the Kyrgyz-Kazakh people one day establish grade schools, the language of instruction in these schools must be the mother tongue. Currently, at the very least, primary education in Kyrgyz-Kazakh schools should be conducted in the native language, and there should be a sufficient number of these schools. The children of Kyrgyz-Kazakh laborers should first receive education in their mother tongue schools. Learning a foreign language too early leads to numerous mistakes, which is incorrect. Knowledge does not lie in the language but in understanding; education is not in speaking Russian, but in fostering good deeds. These can be found in mother tongue and national schools for children. They cannot be found elsewhere, and even if they are, the cost is high. Foreign languages do not aid education, are difficult to understand, and only become obstacles. All of this indicates that the highest priority for the Kyrgyz-Kazakh people is to establish a sufficient number of well-structured primary national schools. Children should not bypass national schools to study foreign languages, thereby creating difficulties for themselves..." [7, 2009, pp. 123-125].

After the October Revolution, proletarian culturalists dominated the literary front. According to them, every era has literature that corresponds to it; in the era of the rich, there is rich literature, while in the era of proletarian rule, only proletarian literature exists, with no place for other literatures. Proletarian culturalists attempted to dismiss all old literature as historical refuse, labeling "white-collar" writers as "bourgeois" and persecuting them. Kazakh national liberation writers who had gathered around the Alash Autonomy were persecuted. Some fled Kazakhstan, seeking refuge in Tashkent. There, dedicated individuals like N. Turekulov and S. Kozhanov did their utmost to provide them with assistance and care.

Now, let us return to S. Kozhanov's work and remarkable achievements in the field of journalism. The "Ak Zhol" newspaper, published in Tashkent and edited by S. Kozhanov, truly became a hub for gathering of Kazakh creative intellectuals during these years. Writers such as Mirjaqyp Dulatov, Magzhan Zhumabayev, Zhusupbek Aimautov, Abdulla Baitasov, Ilyas Zhansugurov, and Birali Suleev frequently contributed their works to this publication.

Nazir and Sultanbek assisted Zhusupbek Aimautov in securing the position of principal at the Shymkent Pedagogical Technical School; they provided refuge for the persecuted Mukhtar Auezov; they also facilitated Magzhan Zhumabayev's journey to Moscow and helped him gain admission to the Literary Institute.

Just as those patriotic social activists who know their nation's history and culture well can stand out at the national level, S. Kozhanov had a profound understanding of his people's history, culture, and literature, dedicating his life to the future of his nation. Despite the varied opinions of his contemporaries regarding Abai's political views, Sultanbek regarded him as a spiritual father. He believed Akhmet Baitursynuly was the

heir to the great poet's legacy and tradition, and he himself followed this path. In an era when shortsighted post-revolutionary policies tarnished the cultural heritage of the past, Sultanbek defended Abai and Akhmet, writing: "When discussing the revolution among Kazakhs, one cannot overlook Abai Kunanbayev and Akhmet Baitursynov. Can anyone doubt their significant contributions to the revolutionary progress among Kazakhs? All current revolutionaries are students of Abai and Akhmet." [7].

Sultanbek Kozhanov wrote the preface for the poetry collection of Magzhan, who was widely known for his poems created for the nation and the people, published in the "Kazakh" newspaper. At that time, even discussing Magzhan was politically perilous, let alone publishing his poems. Thus, Sultanbek's action can be regarded as a deliberate and courageous feat.

In 1924, an article titled "Magzhan" was published in the newspaper "Ak Zhol," echoing and further elaborating on the views expressed in Sultanbek's preface for M. Zhumabayev's book. The article states: "The poets following Abai did not have a coarse language, but among recent poets, no one has done more than Magzhan to infuse poetry with sweet melodies, delicate emotions, and gentle language" (Ak Zhol, April 1, 1924). Professor A. Sharip, a researcher on Sultanbek, believes that "this article was either written based on Sultanbek's suggestions or authored by him" [7, 2009, p. 311].

S. Kozhanov held a central position in Kazakh literary life during the 1920s, continually presenting bold and vibrant ideas on core literary issues. Amidst the turbulent period of the 1920s, Sultanbek courageously opposed those who dismissed Abai and the entirety of Kazakh literary heritage, as well as the proponents of extreme pauperism and "proletarian culturalism" in literature. When Magzhan faced persecution, Sultanbek was the first to recognize his greatness, publish his works, and highly praise his poetic talent. He recorded the history of Kazakh literature and culture with a golden pen.

The talented Sultanbek, amidst his engagement with national and social affairs, frequently expressed his emotions through poetry, capturing them on paper.

"Will it not please if I too recite a poem?
Do poets not create something out of nothing?
If I weave and rhyme my words into a verse,
Will an ignoramus pretend to be wise and criticize it?" [7, 2009, p. 217].

Poems such as "What Should I Do" ("Qayteyin"), "Who is Responsible?" ("Kim Zhauapti?"), "Think About It" ("Oylap Korshi"), "Who is This?" ("Bul Kim?"), "What Should I Say?" ("Neni Aytayin?"), "Young Squad" ("Zhas Kosyn"), "We Will See" ("Koremiz"), "Our Aspirations" ("Tilegimiz"), "Seemingly True Opinions" ("Shynga Usagan Pikirler"), and "Critique for Translators" ("Tilmashtarga bir Sin") were published in various periodicals.

During his tenure in important positions, S. Kozhanov closely integrated his primary responsibilities with social, scientific, literary, critical, and political writing. Scholar Amantai Sharip discovered 135 articles and several poems by Sultanbek, published under the pseudonyms "Topak," "Tarpan," and "Zamandas," in newspapers

such as "Birlik Tui," "Ak Zhol," "Enbekshil Kazakh," and "Tilshi," as well as in magazines like "Sholpan," "Kyzyl Kazakhstan," "Jas Kairat," "Leninshil Zhas," and "Sana." These works were compiled into a book [7, 2009, p. 352].

S. Kozhanov's political essays are characterized by their wide range of themes covering social, economic, and cultural life. They boldly address pressing issues, are incisive and specific in language, richly supported by evidence, and concise. From brief news items to in-depth feature articles, he explored nearly every newspaper genre. His broad vision, extensive knowledge, and exceptional skill in expressing ideas captivate readers.

Poet A. Baitursynov wrote "Language Tool" ("Til Kural") and "Literary Studies" ("Adebiet Tanytkysh"), while poet M. Zhumabayev authored "Pedagogy" ("Pedagogika"). Writer Zh. Aimautov penned "Psychology" ("Psixologiya"), poet S. Seifullin wrote "Kazakh Literature" ("Qazaq Adebieti"), and writer M. Auezov composed "History of Literature" ("Adebiet Tarihi"). Additionally, railway worker M. Tynyshbayev and doctor S. Asfendiyarov authored "History of Kazakhstan" ("Qazaqstan Tarihi"). In this context, to meet the needs of the arithmetic curriculum, S. Kozhanov wrote the textbook "Arithmetic Tools" ("Eseptanu Kuraly") for secondary schools in 1924.

In the final years of his life, S. Kozhanov, who held various positions in Uzbekistan, was constantly subjected to accusations of "Kozhanovism," "Pan-Turkism," "nationalism," and "separatism." Extreme activists and radical communists in Kazakhstan relentlessly created problems for Sultanbek, even from afar in Tashkent, demanding public apologies for his alleged "Kozhanovism" and "nationalism."

S. Kozhanov dedicated his life to the path of national revival, clearly expressing his views, openly battling his opponents, and making every effort to realize his ideals. However, the imperial policies of the Kremlin continuously obstructed his aspirations for freedom. The Kremlin did not dare to send him back to his homeland, Kazakhstan, preferring instead to utilize his talents to develop Uzbekistan's national economy. Additionally, the authorities in Kazakhstan, who were close to the Kremlin, also took measures to prevent S. Kozhanov's return.

S. Kozhanov was arrested on July 16, 1937 in Tashkent and on February 10, 1938, he was executed in Moscow by a military tribunal along with Nazir Torekulov and Turar Ryskulov on charges of being "enemies of the people." The colonizers took the life of the brilliant Sultanbek, whose radiance was like that of a morning star, at the prime age of 44. This eagle, who soared from Aksumbe at the northern foot of the Karatau Mountains, matured in Turkistan, and valiantly flew for the future of his nation in Kazakhstan, ultimately sacrificed his life in a foreign land. It was later confirmed that his remains were interred at the Kommunarka shooting ground near Moscow, formerly a site of the PCIA (People's Commissariat for Internal Affairs).

Conclusion. The archives and rare book collections of the National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi in Tashkent contain many valuable materials on the history of Kazakh periodicals. These archives hold numerous informative documents about Kazakh intellectuals who played significant roles in the socio-political life of the Turkistan region. In particular, the archives provide extensive

information on prominent figures such as M. Shokai, M. Tynyshpayev, T. Ryskulov, S. Kozhanov, N. Torekulov, S. Seifullin, S. Asfendiyarov, M. Zhumabayev, Zh. Aimautov, I. Toktybayev, H. Dosmukhamedov, D. Dosmukhamedov, G. Muratbayev, T. Zhurgenov, A. Sergaziev, S. Eskarayev, Konyr-Kozha Kozhikov, A. Orazbayev, E. Omarov, and Kh. Bolganbaev, which would intrigue any researcher. The earliest Kazakh newspaper, "Turkistan Vilaytinin Gazeti," which met the spiritual needs of the Kazakh nation from 1870 to 1883, along with valuable materials on newspapers and journals such as "Birlik Tui," "Ak Zhol," "Alash," "Kedei Ainasy," "Zhas Kairat," "Sholpan," and "Sana," still require further in-depth research.

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